

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MALADAPTIVE SCHEMAS IN SOCIAL ANXIETY

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Abstract

This research paper aims to reveal the intricate relationship between social anxiety and maladaptive schemas as delineated by Young. Specifically, it delves into the association that exists between the degree of social anxiety and 18 distinct maladaptive schemas which are grouped into five domains. The empirical findings from this research highlight the presence of a significant correlation between elevated levels of social anxiety and the negativity/pessimism schema, as well as the overvigilance/inhibition domain. Furthermore, this study establishes a statistically significant relationship between the increased levels of social anxiety and the defectiveness/shame schema. Individuals with high levels of social anxiety scored high/average on the Young's Schemas Questionnaire.

By using the Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale, it became feasible to identify the situations and interactions that are closely linked to elevated social anxiety levels. The study revealed that social scenarios characterized by formal interactions, such as public speaking or self-presentation in front of an audience, were the most anxiety-inducing experiences for the surveyed participants.

Keywords: social anxiety, maladaptive schemas, negativity/pessimism schema, overvigilance/inhibition domain.

It is common for individuals to encounter anxiety in various social contexts, and this is considered a typical human response. The opinions of others hold significance for people. When anxiety reaches excessive levels, it can lead to negative thoughts that impede effective behavior.

Social anxiety, clinically referred to as social phobia, is characterized by an intense fear or anxiety that is related to one or more social situations, associated with excessive sensitivity to perceived scrutiny and evaluation by others, as defined by the DSM-5. Such social situations encompass interpersonal interactions, such as meeting people or engaging in face-to-face conversations, as well as activities performed in the presence of others, including dining in public, working under supervision, and speaking before an audience during presentations or speeches.

Based on the 2020 data provided by the Anxiety and Depression Association of America (ADAA), more than 15 million Americans aged 18 and older experience high levels of social anxiety, accounting for 7.1% of the population. Notably, these statistics are on an upward trajectory. While the current situation in Georgia remains undocumented, there is a discernible rise in referrals to specialists for anxiety disorders. The interest, and willingness to discuss topics about mental health are progressing significantly. As a result, the urgency of addressing this issue is paramount.

It is essential to highlight that the existing body of scientific literature in the Georgian language concerning social anxiety is notably scarce and limited, especially research on maladaptive schemas. Consequently,

there is a dearth of Georgian-language materials related to this topic. The data obtained from this study will contribute to the formation of a new area of research on the issue and the growth of future research interests related to the topic.

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the correlation between social anxiety levels and maladaptive schemas. Specifically, it seeks to ascertain whether the intensity of maladaptive schemas increases as social anxiety levels rise. Additionally, the research aims to pinpoint which among the 18 maladaptive schemas exhibits the most pronounced associations with the social anxiety variable and delineate the specific nature of these connections.

As described by Dobson, schemas are enduring mental representations of objects, individuals, and concepts, encompassing the relationships between them. The development of schemas commences in early childhood and is grounded in the thoughts and ideas acknowledged, articulated, and established by the individual's environment. These schemas evolve as individuals age, with previously acquired information integrating with real-life experiences, either reinforcing or challenging existing schemas. Schemas are directed toward the self, others, and the external world, influencing various cognitive processes. One of the high importance in such processes is memory bias, which can support these schemas.

Based on the research objectives, the Liebowitz Social Anxiety Assessment Scale (LSAS) and Young's Schemas Questionnaire (YSQ-L3) were employed as the measuring instruments. These questionnaires were

combined as two sections within a Google Form and distributed to the selected participants, who were recruited through convenience sampling. The questionnaire's instructions contained essential information regarding the study's purpose, the instruments used, and the overall procedure. Participants were assured that the principles of anonymity and confidentiality would be rigorously upheld.

The Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale was used to assess an individual's level of social anxiety in social interactions and behavioral responses within social situations. On the other hand, Young's Schemas Questionnaire (YSQ-L3) was utilized to measure all 18 maladaptive schemas. The questionnaire presents statements that essentially convey beliefs, opinions, or assumptions. Respondents were asked to evaluate their agreement with each statement, indicating the extent to which these provisions resonated with their own experiences and beliefs.

The relationship between social anxiety and maladaptive schemas has been studied by numerous authors. For instance, a 2014 Australian study aimed to establish a connection between social anxiety and early maladaptive schemas. This study, comprising 360 participants, revealed that individuals with high scores in social anxiety also scored high in the disconnection/rejection domain. Research has also found that temperament has a significant influence on the choice of coping strategies.

In the context of social anxiety, individuals with a more introverted temperament tend to resort to avoidance behavior as a coping strategy (26, 171-190).

In a 2006 study conducted in Portugal, individuals with social anxiety demonstrated significantly higher scores across nearly all maladaptive schemas when compared to participants who did not exhibit substantial anxiety levels. This study also demonstrated that individuals with social anxiety are less inclined to believe that their need for stable, trustworthy, and empathic relationships will be adequately met (27, 571-584).

A 2008 study discovered that social anxiety is closely associated with the category of schemas related to abandonment, failure, and emotional deprivation. Individuals exhibiting high levels of social anxiety displayed fears of failure, being abandoned by significant others, and fear of being perceived as incompetent. Furthermore, they believed it was essential to conceal their true emotions to avoid rejection from others (Calvete, Orue, 2008).

These findings suggest a robust link between social anxiety and cognitive patterns related to unmet emotional needs, pessimistic social expectations, concerns about abandonment and failure, interpersonal anxiety, etc.

Drawing from the findings of previous studies, it is reasonable to suggest that an escalation in social anxiety levels would likely correspond to an increase in the intensity of maladaptive schemas. Significant relationships can probably be observed with schemas such as abandonment/instability, emotional inhibition, failure, negativity/pessimism, emotional deprivation, defectiveness/shame, and the domain of other-directedness.

In our study, 30 out of the 115 respondents scored above-average levels on the Liebowitz Social Anxiety Assessment Scale (LSAS). None of the respondents reached the maximum score on LSAS, which ranges from 80 to 95 and above. As a result, moderately elevated levels of social anxiety were identified in 26% of the respondents, with 23 being female and 7 being male (Female - 77%, Male - 23%). Furthermore, 11 respondents in the study scored below the minimum threshold for social anxiety. The majority of participants fell within the low and medium levels of social anxiety (63%). The collected data were processed using SPSS.

A correlational analysis of the data was conducted to determine the relationship between the level of social anxiety and the domains of Young's maladaptive schemas. A statistically significant correlation was found between social anxiety and the domains of maladaptive schemas. In particular, the strongest, positive correlation was established between social anxiety and the overvigilance/inhibition domain ($r = 0.772$, $P < 0.01$). Strong positive correlations were revealed between the level of social anxiety and the domains of disconnection/rejection ($r = 0.626$, $P < 0.01$), and other-directedness ($r = 0.651$, $P < 0.01$). Impaired autonomy and performance domain and social anxiety appeared to have a relatively small but significant positive correlation ($r = 0.407$, $P < 0.01$). A weak negative relationship was established between the domain of limited restrictions and social anxiety ($r = -0.289$, $P < 0.01$).

The mean scores for each maladaptive schema of respondents with elevated social anxiety ($N = 30$) were analyzed to assess the prevalence of these schemas. The scale used had a maximum score of six for each schema. Based on the data obtained, a rating of maladaptive schemas was constructed. It was observed that the schema with the highest mean score was negativity/pessimism ($M = 5.1$). Following this, the schema of unrelenting standards ranked second in terms of frequency and severity ($M = 4.5$). The ranking of the remaining schemas is as follows: social isolation/alienation ($M = 4.3$), and mistrust/abuse ($M = 4.2$). Schemas for self-sacrifice, defectiveness/shame, and vulnerability all had identical mean scores of ($M = 4$).

Those schemas, that had a high prevalence among highly anxious participants, were selected and correlation analysis was performed with the variable of social anxiety. For each participant, schema scores were analyzed in relationship to social anxiety scores. The results of the correlation analysis revealed that the negativity/pessimism schema demonstrated the highest positive correlation with the level of social anxiety ($r = 0.524$, $P < 0.01$). Additionally, a statistically significant correlation was observed between the level of social anxiety and the defectiveness/shame schema ($r = 0.411$, $P < 0.01$). The isolation/alienation schema also exhibited a significant correlation with the level of social anxiety ($r = 0.311$, $P < 0.01$). Conversely, the correlation between social anxiety and other schemas, like self-sacrifice ($r = 0.289$, $P < 0.01$), unrelenting standards ($r = 0.138$, $P < 0.01$), mistrust/abuse ($r = 0.128$, $P < 0.01$) and vulnerability ($r = 0.123$, $P < 0.01$) was weaker.

Based on the research findings, it is evident that clear and notable associations exist between social anxiety and several maladaptive schemas, specifically, between social anxiety and the negativity/pessimism schema ($r = .524$). Additionally, the intensity of the defectiveness/shame schema was found to increase in tandem with rising social anxiety levels ($r = .411$). In terms of the distribution of the domains, the most robust association with social anxiety was observed in domain 5, identified as overvigilance/inhibition ($r = .0722$). The research has also established that individuals grappling with social anxiety tend to score significantly higher on the Young's Schemas Questionnaire. Furthermore, with regards to classifying social situations, it was determined that for the majority of respondents, a high degree of anxiety was most closely linked to public speaking, with 30.6% of participants reporting this as a significant source of anxiety.

Results

Social anxiety and the domains of isolation/rejection and other-directedness.

A central symptom of social anxiety involves persistent preoccupation, anxiety, and rumination about potentially adverse outcomes that could arise in social situations. This phase is closely associated with what is referred to as prurumination.

Individuals with social anxiety tend to direct their attention predominantly towards negative or potentially negative cues and expectations, as outlined in Heimberg's model. This attention bias can cause positive elements to remain out of focus and go unnoticed.

Social anxiety and defectiveness/shame schema

According to structural models of social anxiety, individuals are attuned to both external stimuli, such as the presence of an audience, and internal features. Among these internal features, the most intricate and generalized is the self-concept (Campbell 1996). The self-concept, on its hand, is shaped by Bandura's patterns of self-esteem and self-efficacy. It's common for individuals with social anxiety to exhibit low self-efficacy. Concurrently, they engage in persistent self-monitoring of their behavior, with the primary aim of avoiding their most undesirable outcome – the feeling of exclusion or unacceptance. This particular item from Young's schema questionnaire encapsulates an intermediate belief or perspective. On one hand, it conveys low self-efficacy, while on the other hand, it's oriented toward the negative outcome that an individual anticipates as social feedback. This is the reason behind their continuous self-monitoring.

Recommendations

The findings of this study provide perspective on the design of future research endeavors, which may delve deeper into the specificity and interrelationships of these variables. To enhance the informativeness of research results, it is recommended to further specify the characteristics associated with these phenomena. For instance, researchers could categorize specific cog-

nitive, emotional, and behavioral patterns of social anxiety and investigate the significance of each in greater detail. Additionally, the theory of maladaptive schemas presents a vast realm for research exploration. Within this scope, it would be intriguing to introduce additional variables that could provide further clarity on the connection between the social anxiety phenomenon and schemas.

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